

PURPOSE OF USING ELECTRONIC EDUCATIONAL LITERATURE IN EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract. *The transition to electronic textbooks in higher education brings many benefits. However, reluctance has been noted by students and publishers, preventing the change from happening sooner. Decision makers (such as the Ministry of Education and university administrations) need to rely on real survey data to plan and implement the best strategy.*

Keywords: *higher education, Carreiro, Emerald Publisher, e-textbooks, PDF file, HTML page, iPad, Amazon's Kindle.*

INTRODUCTION

The recent COVID-19 Pandemic has further institutionalized the applications of digital technologies in education. These digital technologies have made a paradigm shift in the entire education system. It is not only a knowledge provider but also a co-creator of information, a mentor, and an assessor. Technological improvements in education have made life easier for students. Instead of using pen and paper, students nowadays use various software and tools to create presentations and projects. When compared to a stack of notebooks, an iPad is relatively light. When opposed to a weighty book, surfing an E-book is easier. These methods aid in increasing interest in research. This paper is brief about the need for digital technologies in education and discusses major applications and challenges in education. The advent of digital publishing is changing the world of traditional publishing as discussed by Carreiro (2010) and analyzed by Emerald Publisher (2012). In both areas, recent technological advances in e-book reading, as well as in e-book storage techniques and standards (e.g. the new E-PUB 3 standard) have been a catalyst for the transition from print to e-learning guides (e-textbooks) is serving From an industry perspective, the e-book market, where consumer electronic products such as the iPad or Amazon's Kindle are widespread, offers room for healthy competition and innovation, opening up a world of possibilities. As the transition to e-book adoption is slowly taking place around the world, it represents a dramatic shift in how books are created, managed, distributed, and consumed. Publishers and readers alike are adapting to the emerging new landscape, each to their own advantage.

Before moving on to the adoption of an e-book, it is necessary to define the term "e-textbook". Although printed textbooks are self-defined, a definition of e-textbook is not necessary. In this survey, an e-textbook is a digital material that can be accessed and read on a portable device, such as a laptop, e-reader, smartphone, tablet, or desktop computer. Initially, e-textbooks were just a collection of PDF files or HTML pages, called the digital version of a printed textbook. Nowadays, with the advanced capabilities of e-books, e-textbooks can include interactive elements such as audio, video, animation, simulation, live experiments, and more. In addition, they have inherited all the attributes provided by the Internet for information organization, e.g. real-time interaction with links, online dictionaries and other resources. This is a move that could benefit

students and publishers greatly. Data notebooks bring several benefits to the learning process from a learning perspective.

Textbooks, whether printed or electronic, should meet students' requirements for annotation, quick reference, smart indexing, bookmarking, etc. Instant access to content with just a few clicks is also a huge advantage for readers compared to visiting a library or bookstore to get a hard copy. In particular, recent advancements in the learning process provide interactivity with e-book content, in addition to e-book search capabilities and other benefits.

Furthermore, the concept of reuse, especially in academic publications, allows students to combine and reuse materials that cover the same topic but come from different sources, such as book chapters, or even embedded and potentially interactive learning objects. will give.

The role of e-learning resources in increasing the effectiveness of education. Fundamental reforms, the development of science and technology and technologies in our country, and the requirements of the transition to an information society are leading to a change in the educational strategy. New forms of continuous education, including network, informational, distance and innovative educational technologies based on modern teaching technologies, have emerged. The main reason for the emergence of new types of education based on information and communication technologies is the traditional method of the former education system, which has been formed over the years in successfully solving the tasks of imparting knowledge to people from different classes of society, regularly improving their skills and retraining. and means are limited. In such a situation, it is important to form a continuous education system based on information and communication technologies, relying on the potential of higher educational institutions. Improving the effectiveness of the teaching process is becoming an urgent issue of modern pedagogy. The rapid development of technology, technology and production requires that students studying in higher education and academic lyceums and vocational colleges have the knowledge and skills appropriate to this development.

The need to raise the teaching methods to a completely new level in order to give the students the skills to master the new achievements of technology and technology remains the demand of the time. In solving this important task, it is inevitable that the wide use of modern pedagogic and information - communication technologies, electronic educational resources, which are rapidly entering everyday life, will play an important role. Currently, the use of tested special media: electronic educational resources, virtual stands, animation programs added to computer equipment, audio and video tools are effective for students' mastery of the lessons. it is destined to give results. The process of organizing lessons with the help of electronic educational resources effectively helps students to receive the knowledge they receive not only through hearing, but also through visual senses and to deeply understand the ideas and content of concepts.

THE PLACE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF ELECTRONIC EDUCATION IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

In general, the advantages of e-learning can be summarized as follows possible: Method of teaching students. There are no time limits for classes. Always a lot versatility, coverage, portability, timeliness, and meeting learning needs. The quality of lessons increases (based on the use of multimedia tools). Teaching effectiveness and return increase (at the expense of removing time and space restrictions).

Using different media. Information and knowledge One of the important means of communication to the audience is the relevant mass media is to use.

Text, sound, picture, animation and video are important means of communication in virtual education uses five media such as Equal presence. Virtual education is an equal educational tool for all participants enables use. That is, a whole from one well-designed virtual lesson can be used by readers across the country or even wider.

Extensive training. Currently, some of the types of education are worldwide It does not have the ability to spread as a virtual education through the Internet. Virtual learning environment the geographical boundaries of its distribution correspond to the boundaries of the Internet. Thus, this type of education provides an opportunity to learn from anywhere. Virtual classes in automatic mode are available 24 hours a day. Thus, virtual learners can revise their lessons, exercises and tests at any time of the day. Therefore, the virtual learning audience can attend classes, complete assignments and take appropriate tests at any time of the day. Thus, another feature of virtual education is time lack of restrictions.

E-learning to connect teachers and students around the world ability, which is a huge advantage. Interaction between teacher and student. Teacher and students in the classroom physical participation is not required. Time and travel costs for students are reduced. Ability to teach large numbers of students in a classroom. The ability to record the activities of teachers and the progress of students. Ability to create different models of teaching by the teacher. Ease of communication.

Mutual cooperation. Other advantages of virtual education through the Internet includes the use of means of communication, consultation and cooperation between the teacher and the student.

For example, most e-learning management systems have email and chat capabilities. With these tools you can send messages, questions to give, to discuss your scientific articles and conversations among the participants possible.

The role of electronic educational resources

It is important to increase the interest and activity of students in the study process is a pedagogical problem. Modern information and communication technologies are great in increasing the activity and interest of a person, organizing and managing his cognitive process is distinguished by having didactic capabilities. In this regard, the creation of electronic educational resources from subjects is of particular importance.

The content of electronic educational resources includes electronic textbooks and training manuals, instructions, sets of exercises and problems, hypertext and multimedia tools, methodological including manuals, electronic tests and assignments, electronic dictionary, and other resources that ensure the student's independent learning.

Providing students with appropriate teaching and methodical materials for teaching subjects through information technologies in a modern form, that is, in the form of electronic educational resources can be recommended.

CONCLUSION

The fact that a number of authors are introducing topics with the help of various electronic teaching tools, in which it is possible to be directly sure that the level of knowledge of students is increasing. organization of the education and training process should be the primary task of every leader and pedagogue. In our opinion, special attention should be paid to the following when using e-learning tools:

- development of methodological students to be included in educational materials;

- do not exceed the duration of using animation programs for more than 25-30 minutes;
- the concepts of the presented topic are discussed by the teacher and students in a two-way communication;
- achieving that the students will rework the presented films independently and form new concepts;
- determination of criteria for evaluation of teaching results

It is known that pedagogical and information technologies used in the educational process are divided into several types, the most important of which is teaching with the help of computer equipment. Based on this, taking into account the requirements for electronic textbooks and virtual stands, it is appropriate to develop and use the electronic version of lectures, laboratory work, and practical training in chemistry. Therefore, it is possible to bring virtual pictures from the science of chemistry on the topics of periodic system of elements and atomic structure. In this picture, the structure of all elements in the periodic system of elements is created in the style of animation, in which the student can create a clear image by seeing the arrangement of the nucleus of the atom of each element and the arrangement of the particles around it, the spatial position of the laws of their movement.

Most importantly, recent technological advances have made it possible to include dynamic, interactive content in electronic textbooks, which helps the learning process.

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